

Synthesis of Some New Hydroxytriazenes

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THE new class of chelating agents, hydroxytriazenes, is of comparatively recent origin. Bamberger *et al*¹ and Gebhard and Thompson² are accredited for synthesising a number of hydroxytriazenes for the first time. The complexing ability of these compounds was examined by Elkins and Hunter³. However, Sogani and Bhattacharya⁴ were the first to evaluate their analytical usefulness.

These compounds have been named as diazo-hydroxyamino compounds and triazene oxides (the azoxy analogue in the triazene series)⁵. However, Sogani *et al*, have preferred to name the compounds as 3-hydroxytriazene family of reagents.

The compounds possess the common functional grouping $-N(OH)-N=N-$. Analytical applications of this class of organic reagents were first reviewed by Purohit⁶. Subsequently, Chakraborti and Majumdar⁷ reviewed the work done during the decade 1967-76.

Three methods of preparation of hydroxytriazenes are described in literature. The first method given by Bamberger *et al* and Gebhard and Thompson consists in reducing nitro- or nitrosobenzene with phenyl or substituted phenyl hydrazines. The second method given by Sogani and Bhattacharya and Elkins and Hunter makes use of the coupling reaction of alkyl or aryl-hydroxylamines with diazonium salts in acetate buffered solutions at 0°. Mitsuhashi and Simamura⁸ gave the third method in which oxidation of diazo-amino benzenes with peroxy-benzoic acid in ether gives the corresponding diaryl hydroxytriazenes. However, the second method is more commonly followed because of its general applicability, ease of preparation and better yield. In the present communication synthesis of ten more hydroxytriazenes with some of their physical properties studied and qualitative spot tests with α -naphthyl amine and picric acid are reported.

General method of preparation :

The nitrocompounds were converted to their respective hydroxylamines by reduction with zinc dust and ammonium chloride. To an aqueous solution of this freshly prepared alkyl or aryl hydroxylamine crushed ice was added in sufficient quantity and then kept in the ice bath to keep the temperature at 0°. A diazotised solution of substituted anilines in molar proportion was added slowly under mechanical stirring. In all the cases a concentrated solution of sodium acetate was added in small lots

TABLE I

Hydroxytriazenes				Cryst. from	m.p. °C	Colour and shape of crystals	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			
R	R'	R''	R'''				C	H	N	X
CH ₃	H	Cl	H	Alcohol and water	66	Light yellow needles	45.11 (45.29)	4.31 (4.34)	22.48 (22.66)	18.88 (19.10)
CH ₃	H	COOH	H	Alcohol	185	Shining orange-red platelets	49.12 (49.23)	4.58 (4.64)	21.27 (21.58)	
CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	Ethyl acetate	178	Yellowish brown microcrystalline	42.56 (42.85)	3.79 (4.11)	28.32 (28.56)	
CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	60% Alcohol	100	Dark violet plates	53.97 (53.03)	6.01 (6.12)	22.76 (23.19)	
CH ₃	H	COCH ₃	H	Alcohol	146	Violet-red plates	55.86 (55.94)	5.41 (5.78)	21.45 (21.76)	
CH ₃	H	H	Br	Alcohol and water	149	Light buff silky needles	36.39 (36.54)	3.47 (3.50)	17.97 (18.26)	Br= 34.36 (34.79)
CH ₃	H	H	SO ₃ Na	Water	300 with decomp.	Dark brown rectangular crystals	33.34 (33.20)	2.95 (3.18)	16.37 (16.59)	S= 12.38 (12.66)
CH ₃ >CH CH ₃	H	H	SO ₃ Na	20% Alcohol	282 with decomp.	Light brown small crystals	41.51 (41.86)	4.57 (4.68)	16.11 (16.27)	S= 12.29 (12.41)
C ₆ H ₅	H	Cl	H	Alcohol and water	158	Yellowish brown microcrystalline	57.72 (58.19)	4.03 (4.06)	17.12 (16.96)	Cl= 13.98 (14.81)
C ₆ H ₅	H	COCH ₃	H	Benzene	164	Light green plates	65.59 (65.86)	4.98 (5.13)	16.12 (16.46)	

to maintain the pH at about 5. The hydroxytriazenes were obtained in the form of dark coloured granular precipitates. The precipitates were washed with ice cold water except the sulphonato derivatives which are soluble in water. The solvents used for crystallization, m.p. etc have been given in Table 1.

Two methods for spot test detection of hydroxytriazenes were reported by Purohit^{8,10}. The basis of the first test is the formation of pink colour when an acetic acid solution of α -naphthyl amine is added to an acetic acid solution of hydroxytriazenes. The second method consisted of adding 2 to 5 drops of saturated ethanolic solution of picric acid to either a pinch of solid hydroxytriazene or a drop of its ethanolic solution to give a pink to red colour or precipitate.

α -Naphthylamine method : One drop of hydroxytriazene solution in acetic acid (0.001% w/v) was treated in a small test tube with 2 drops of acetic acid solution (0.01% w/v) of α -naphthyl amine. Immediate development of pink or reddish brown colour took place. Gentle warming of the test solution further intensified the colour. The results of the tests are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Hydroxytriazenes				Colour with α -naphthyl amine
R	R'	R''	R'''	
CH ₃	H	Cl	H	Pinkish red on warming
CH ₃	H	COOH	H	Light pink on warming
CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	Yellow. Test not given
CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	Reddish brown on warming
CH ₃	H	COCH ₃	H	No colour in cold. Light pink on heating
CH ₃	H	H	Br	No colour in cold. Light pink on warming
CH ₃	H	H	SO ₂ Na	Aqueous solution of HT gave violet colour on warming
CH ₃ > CH	H	H	SO ₂ Na	Light pink in cold
CH ₃	H	H	H	Intensified on heating
C ₆ H ₅	H	Cl	H	Pink in cold. Intensified red on warming
C ₆ H ₅	H	COCH ₃	H	Intense red colour immediately

Picric acid method :

One drop of a solution of hydroxytriazene (0.001% w/v in ethanol) or a pinch of the solid hydroxytriazene with 2-5 drops of a saturated solution of picric acid were taken in a small test tube and heated for 1 min over a water bath at 55-60°. Pink, violet or reddish brown colour developed. In some cases the colour development took place even in cold but heating further intensified it. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3

Hydroxytriazenes				Colour on heating with picric acid
R	R'	R''	R'''	
CH ₃	H	Cl	H	Immediate pink in cold Dark red on heating
CH ₃	H	COOH	H	Reddish brown
CH ₃	H	NO ₂	H	Reddish brown
CH ₃	H	OCH ₃	H	Red in cold. Intensified on heating
CH ₃	H	COCH ₃	H	Reddish brown
CH ₃	H	H	Br	Reddish brown
CH ₃	H	H	SO ₂ Na	Aqueous solution of the HT gave intense red colour
CH ₃ > CH	H	H	SO ₂ Na	Light pink, which intensified on heating
C ₆ H ₅	H	Cl	H	Intense red
C ₆ H ₅	H	COCH ₃	H	Intense red

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